

PROBLEMATICS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE LITERACY MOVEMENT

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Abstract

The literacy movement faces several challenges in its implementation, especially the literacy movement in Indonesia. This literature study aimed to analyze the problems and implementation of the literacy movement in Indonesia using the literature study method. Data was collected by searching articles and journals related to the literacy movement in Indonesia. The results of the analysis showed that the government plays an important role in increasing public interest in reading through various programs and policies that support the literacy movement. However, there are still obstacles to implementing the program, such as a lack of budget and a lack of coordination between the agencies involved. In addition, the importance of considering local wisdom in developing literacy programs in Indonesia was also emphasized. The role of the family and school in increasing literacy is also very important. Other obstacles include the lack of access to reading materials and technology to support literacy, the lack of public awareness of the importance of literacy, and the lack of quality and quantity of human resources related to literacy. In overcoming the problems of the literacy movement, the implementation of effective programs involving the government, educational institutions, families, and society as a whole is very important. The results of this literature study are expected to contribute to the development of the literacy movement in Indonesia.

Keywords: problems, implementation, literacy movement

INTRODUCTION

Literacy plays an important role in developing human potential and improving the quality of life. In Indonesia, the literacy movement is the government's main focus to increase public literacy. In 2017, the government started a literacy movement to encourage interest in reading and developing reading habits from an early age.

This literacy movement has been running for several years but there are still many challenges and obstacles that need to be overcome so that the literacy movement becomes more effective. The philosophical basis of the literacy movement in Indonesia is the Pancasila philosophy, namely

cooperation because the literacy movement is not only the responsibility of the government but also the collective responsibility of society.

Formally, the literacy movement in Indonesia has also been regulated in Law Number 43 of 2007 concerning Libraries and Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 16 of 2019 concerning the National Literacy Movement. The literacy movement in Indonesia is not only supported by philosophical and juridical foundations but also by many literary studies that have been carried out by experts.

A lack of support from family, environment, and school can be a factor

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inhibiting Indonesian people's interest in reading (Arsyad & Sutriani, 2020). The success of the literacy movement in a country does not only depend on government programs but also the involvement of the community and the private sector (Pappas & Pendlebury, 2018). Therefore, there needs to be synergy between the government, families, schools, communities, and the private sector in developing the literacy movement in Indonesia.

Based on the discussion above as well as findings from various literature studies, the author hopes that this literature study can contribute to strengthening the literacy movement in Indonesia and encourage people to be more active in reading and increase literacy levels in Indonesia.

METHOD

This research was conducted using the literature study method. Literature study or library research was research by collecting references or relevant sources such as books, magazines, or scientific articles. The literature study was carried out by searching for credible sources in national and international journals related to problems and solutions in the literacy movement in Indonesia.

Source searches were carried out through academic databases such as Google Scholar and ScienceDirect using keywords such as "literacy movement", "literacy problems", "literacy solutions", and "implementation of literacy movements".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The literacy movement is an important issue in the world of education today, including in Indonesia. Several journals have proposed various solutions to increase people's literacy and interest in reading in Indonesia. The government plays an important role in increasing people's interest in reading through various programs and policies that support the literacy movement (Fauziah & Usman, 2019).

However, there are still many obstacles to implementing the program, such as a lack of budget and lack of coordination between the agencies involved.

The importance of considering local wisdom in developing literacy programs in Indonesia (Suratha, 2019). Respecting local culture and applying methods that are relevant to local culture can increase people's reading interest and literacy.

On the other hand, reading programs in schools can increase students' interest in reading and reading skills. This program includes activities such as shared reading, independent reading, and group discussions about the books read. The importance of the family's role in increasing literacy in Indonesia.

The family can be a conducive environment for improving children's literacy through the practice of reading together and providing access to books that suit the child's interests and needs (Jannah et al., 2020). The role of libraries in increasing community literacy is also important in the context of the literacy movement in Indonesia (Kurniawan & Sukirlan, 2020; Anam & Suhandi, 2020; Turmudi, 2020; Nurhadi, 2021).

However, there are still several obstacles to implementing the literacy movement in Indonesia, such as minimal access to reading materials and literacy-supporting technology, minimal public awareness of the importance of literacy, and minimal quality and quantity of human resources related to literacy. Therefore, the role of the government, educational institutions, families, and society as a whole is very important in realizing the goals of the literacy movement in Indonesia.

Based on the results of the literature study conducted, it can be concluded that the literacy movement in Indonesia still faces many challenges and obstacles. Several solutions compiled based on literature studies have obtained the following results.

Increase access to reading materials and literacy-supporting technology. The use of information and communication technology (ICT) can be a solution to increase access to reading materials and literacy-supporting technology (Suryanto & Mawardi, 2020). The government can develop programs to expand access to digital libraries and e-book platforms, as well as

provide free internet access in unreached areas.

Increase public awareness of the importance of literacy. Effective outreach programs and literacy campaigns can increase public awareness of the importance of literacy (Hadi, 2020). The government, educational institutions, and community organizations must work together to develop creative and innovative outreach programs and literacy campaigns.

Improving the quality and quantity of human resources related to literacy. Training and skills development for teachers and library staff can improve the quality and quantity of human resources related to literacy (Widodo et al., 2019). The government and educational institutions can develop training and skills development programs for teachers and library staff, as well as guarantee the availability of funds and other necessary resources.

Developing a family literacy education model. Family can be a conducive environment for increasing children's literacy (Fauziah & Usman, 2020). Therefore, it is necessary to develop an effective family literacy education model, such as a shared reading program, providing access to books that suit children's interests and needs, and developing an environment that supports literacy activities at home.

Through the implementation of these solutions, it is hoped that the literacy movement in Indonesia can become more effective in increasing the literacy of Indonesian society.

CONCLUSION

This literature study showed that the literacy movement in Indonesia still faces many challenges and obstacles. However, various solutions that have been proposed in the literature can make a significant contribution to increasing the effectiveness of the literacy movement in Indonesia. In the long term, increasing literacy will bring positive changes to society and contribute to the nation's progress. Therefore, there needs to be strong support from the government, educational institutions, and society to achieve this goal. The solutions that can be

given are: increasing access to reading materials and technology; increasing public awareness of the importance of literacy; increasing the quality and quantity of human resources related to literacy; and developing a family literacy education model.

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